

Proving
Georg Cantor's set theory
Is Not True!

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I prove that to begin with there is no infinite list of binary strings and so no infinite sets because all the binary strings digits cannot be listed out 1 by 1 in an infinite list and all the binary strings cannot be listed out 1 by 1 in an infinite list because everything that is infinite has no end and infinity has no end and so since there is no infinite list of binary strings and so no infinite sets, there is no binary strings missing from the list and so there is no hierarchy of larger and larger infinite sets and actually all infinite sequences are equal in size because all infinite sequences have no end by equaling a number that has no end and so cannot be counted and so this is shown by the

extended real number line having

no end at the point at ∞ at the
end of the extended real number line

and so ∞ is the

largest extended real number of
all extended real numbers and so

∞ is the largest number of

all numbers in existence (infinity ∞)!